

PROBLEMS AND REMEDIES OF TEACHER EDUCATION

Prof. Dr. Mrs. Arati P. Sapkale

(Associate Professor)

D.E.S College of Education, Dhule

ABSTRACT

This paper is focuses on the current problems and remedies of teacher education institutions. Teacher education is an important system to improve the quality of school education. The success of educational process depends to a rigid extent on the characteristics and ability of the teacher who is the corner stone of the arch of education the government of India realizes the importance of teacher education as a result of which many reforms were brought out particularly after independence.

Privatization The teacher education has already started showing its tremendous impact on teacher education , while there has been a substantial increase in the number of teacher education institutions in recent years. So lately mushroom growth of private B.Ed. institutions has created a formidable problems. There is a need to resort to some specific affirmative action for improving teacher education.

INTRODUCTION-

Teacher education system is an important vehicle to improve the quality of school education. The success of educational process depends to a rigid extent on the characteristics and ability of the teacher. The teacher education is of two types first is Pre-service and second is In-service. Pre-service teacher education refers to preparation of freshers for the teaching profession. The main objective of the present paper is to examine the current problems and suggest the remedies of teacher education.

PROBLEMS OF TEACHER EDUCATION-

1)High demand of fee and admission process –Most of the self financing teacher education institutions are charging high fee from the students in the form of bus fee, excursion, uniform, study material fee etc.

Also admission process is so hectic and lengthy. The entrance test(CET) is administered for selecting B.Ed. or M.Ed. students, but in this test candidates basic skills in reading, writing and communication is not assessed.

2)Duration- The present duration of B.Ed. and M.Ed. course makes more exam. Oriented and not oriented for professional preparation. The main purpose of teacher education programme is to

develop healthy and broad attitude, interest, values, personality consistent with the dignity of training profession. But this is not possible due to late admission process.

3) Recruitment and quality of staff-- In most of the institutions teachers and assistant professors are not qualified as per NCTE norms. It is also seen that large number of teacher education institutions offering M.Ed. course without a single Ph.D. holder in their staff list.

4) Infrastructure, ICT facility and Library- Infrastructure facility is the basic requirement of any educational institution. But most of the institutions are ill equipped with resources like playground labs, washrooms and library. The position of the college libraries in teacher education institutions is not so well. Inadequate books, never subscribe any national or international journals and periodicals of subjects. In most of teacher education institutions ICT facilities are not provided properly to students due to insufficient computers and resources.

institutions teacher trainees are not attend the class regularly. They complete their B.Ed. or M.Ed. course like distance mode.

5) Problems of practice teaching-- Teaching practice plays an important role in B.Ed. programmes, and its main purpose is to help the trainees to acquire the power of observation, attention, imagination and a sense of time. But many teacher education institutions do not have practicing schools, and they do not have ample time to practice their skills of teaching which results in poor performance as a teacher.

6) Teaching methodology This is also seen that many of the new faculty members are not competent in their subject. Some teacher educators lack content knowledge and have poor standards of pedagogical skills. This develops a lack of confidence and inferiority in them. Faculty can not refer good books in English, references, and handled computer. Then what quality of teachers do they produce?

7) Demand and supply of teachers- There is a mismatch between demand and supply of trained teachers-area wise, subjectwise, and perspective wise. This is primarily because of an inadequate requirements for teachers. And there has been a substantial increase in the number of teacher education institutions in recent years.

To overcome these problems following remedies should be applied by teacher education institutions.

Remedies—

- 1 Specific fee structure should be fixed by university or NCTE.
- 2 All the admission process should over by 1st July and session in any case should be started by 1st July. None of the institution should be granted permission after 1st July.
- 3 Qualification prescribed by NCTE for the selection of teacher educators must be strictly adhered to and revised and upgrade from time to time, also institutions should be forced to pay salary according as pay scale for qualified staff.

4 The teacher educators should be forced to use recent methodology also there is a provision for teacher educators training of personality development programm and communication skills workshop.

5 Every teacher education institution should conduct practice lesssons carefully as per norms to fill the gaps between theory and practical.

6 There is an urgent need to improve the infrastructure and equip them with good facilities and quality instructional material. Management and universities should be provide financial support to equip the appropriate ICT facilities,and buy good books ,journals.

7 Teacher education institutions should be able to ascertain the specific need of society and in this age of globalization teachers are to be prepared for international job market.

CONCLUSION--

Lastly we can conclude that access and quality of teacher education greatly vary between rural and urban areas. Various efforts have been made to improve teacher education. There is a need to resort to some specific affirmative action for improving teacher education.

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